

A Mathematical Proof That Photons Are the Fundamental Particle of Gravity

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INTRODUCTION:

Through unit analysis, statistical mechanics, and the study of photonics I have developed a mathematical proof that gravity is a result of electrostatic forces caused by the interaction of photons and that photons are the fundamental particles of gravity. The proof demonstrates that Newton's, Planck's, and Einstein's gravity constants are equivalent when and only when the properties of Photons are used. Classical Newtonian physics describe gravity in a two-dimensional world and the Newtonian gravity constant formula is:

$$G = \frac{r^2}{m_1 m_2}$$

*Where r is equal to distance between mass 1 and mass 2.

Planck described gravity in three dimensions using the gravity constant:

$$G = \frac{l_p^3}{m_p t_p^2}$$

*Where l_p is the Planck length, m_p is the Planck mass, and t_p is the Planck time.

Einstein moved us closer to an answer by his gravitational constant which described gravity in four dimensions:

$$k = \frac{8\pi G}{C^4}$$

Einstein's gravity constant holds true except for when large values of light interact with matter.

ANALYSIS AND PROOF:

Photons travel in tightly coupled di-pole pairs of energy quanta (Giertz, 2010) and in a quad-pole arrangement. There is a vertical pair, with a spin up (positive charge) and spin down (negative charge), and the horizontal pair with a spin up (positive charge) and spin down (negative charge). The configuration produces electrostatic forces that propel photons in space and over time; $KE = PE$. $\pi(\tau)$ is used to describe rotation in space with 2π being a full rotation over all four quadrants/dimensions. A whole, split into four parts or quanta (V_u, V_d, H_u, H_d), over four dimensions (2π), gives us the first unit in Einstein's gravitational constant:

$$4 \cdot 2\pi = 8\pi$$

"C" describes the speed of light and by raising "C" to the 4th power/dimension we are tracking the distance travelled by each of the energy quanta with respect to time.

8π can be represented by KE; kinetic energy in space. C^4 can be represented by PE; Potential energy or energy over distance where distance equals rate*time. Rewriting Einstein's gravity constant with the substitutive values we get:

$$k = \frac{KE}{PE} * \frac{G}{1}$$

Setting k equal to 1 and solving for G:

$$\frac{PE}{KE} = G$$

PE and KE maintain a ratio of 1:1 or 1

Planck's gravity constant:

$$G = \frac{l_p^3}{m_p t_p^2}$$

describes G in 3 dimensions where l_p is the plank's length to the 3rd power/dimension (PE: energy over distance with respect to time) in ratio with the Planck mass * Planck time squared (KE: energy in two dimensional space). The ratio is 1:1 resulting in $G = 1$. (Ball, 2007)

Newtons 2-D gravitational constant:

$$G = \frac{r^2}{m_1 * m_2}$$

G is equal to the distance in two dimensions with respect to the mass of object 1 * the mass of object 2. Photons are tightly di-coupled meaning they have a distance of 0 between mass 1 and mass 2 of both the energy quanta and the vertical and horizontal pairs; $r = 0$. Photons have a mass of zero; m_1 and $m_2 = 0$. Photons as the fundamental particle of gravity satisfies the identity:

$$G = \frac{0}{0}$$

While classical mathematics equate $0/0$ to undefined, in graph theory and Einstein's theory of relativity $0/0$ is equal to 1 indicating the singularity. Einstein called this condition independence stating that it is the point in which the system

acts independently of any other system. A paper titled, "Zero Divided by Zero Equals One," describes the Law of Independence in length and provides multiple proofs. (Barukčić, 2018)

Therefore, by substituting the properties of photons as the fundamental particles of gravity where the distance between the two masses is equal to 0 and both the masses are equal to 0:

$$G = \frac{0}{0}$$

$$G = 1$$

Lastly, it is only with the properties of photons that this outcome of independence can be produced.

CONCLUSION:

This paper has presented a mathematical proof that photons are the fundamental particle of Gravity and that their electrostatic forces cause objects to attract. Here I proved that:

$$\frac{C^4}{8\pi} \equiv \frac{l_p^3}{m_p t_p^2} \equiv \frac{r^2}{m_1 m_2}$$

$$\frac{PE}{KE} \equiv G_p \equiv G$$

If and only if using the properties of photons. The proof presented in this paper explains gravitational lensing predicted by Einstein's theory of general relativity and proven in 1979 by astronomers at Kitt Peak National Observatory. (Daley, 2018)

Works Cited

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